

OPTIMIZATION OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF RECURRENT PURULENT OTITIS MEDIA IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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Introduction

Acute otitis media is one of the most common diseases in young children and in the structure of ear diseases reaches 65-70%. At the same time, in 10-45% of cases, the acute process becomes protracted and recurrent.

During the first few years of life, RSO occurs in approximately 20-30% of the child population.

Given the wide prevalence of RSO in children, there is a need to develop an algorithm for effective diagnosis and treatment of this disease.

The purpose of this work is to study the effectiveness of diagnosis and treatment of recurrent otitis media in young children.

Materials and methods: for this study, analysis was performed in 34 children with RSO aged from 1 month to three years. Boys - 19 (55.9%), girls-15 (44.1%). All children, except for a thorough otorhinolaryngological examination, in the presence of otitis media, microflora was determined from the secreted ear, from sensitivity to antibiotics, and a playful tonal threshold audiometry was performed. All children were found to have conductive hearing loss.

Results: As a result of the above treatment, out of 34 children with otitis media, 33 (97%) children had an improved general condition, 1 (3%) had no positive dynamics.

Conclusions: Thus, timely and correct chosen therapy tactics leads to a rapid resolution of the disease, prevents relapses and transition to a chronic form.

